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TRANSFORMATIONAL LEADERSHIP IN PUBLIC AND PRIVATE SCHOOLS: A COMPARATIVE STUDY OF TEACHER PERCEPTIONS AND INSTITUTIONAL IMPACT

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ABSTRACT

The aim of the research paper “Transformational Leadership in Public and Private Schools: A Comparative Study of Teacher Perceptions and Institutional Impact” is to explore the teachers experiences about the responsive roles of educational leaders in different public and private sector schools belonging to various regions of Pakistan. In this regard a phenomenological qualitative research inquiry was conducted based on semi-structured interviews. The sample size was 11 and the population composed of different grade teachers of both genders i.e., male and female. The participants perceptions regarding the school leaders were recorded keeping in view ethical concerns of research. According to Lim (2025) a phenomenological type with purposive sampling technique of research analysis method was utilized to gain insights about teachers real life experiences in their professional education field. (pp. 199-299). Thematic analysis was conducted to analyze the data. The study brought to light that there is a difference of approach in both sector schools. The future of young generation lies in the hands of the educators. However, the respective teachers showed high motivation which is a positive sign that the nation will progress rapidly under the supervision of educational school leaders. The

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teachers are passionate about learning new skills, growing professionally and showcasing their talent under the guidance and support of a visionary leader fostering an ideal learning environment for young minds.

Keywords: Pakistan Education; Transformational Leadership; Emerging Trends in Education; Effective Schools; Teacher Education

Introduction

There exist various stakeholders governing educational system which includes students, teachers, school administrators such as principals, policymakers and government officials, support staff such as doctors librarians, counsellors, etc., community members, business and industrial leaders, higher education institutions, media and advocacy groups. Each stakeholder has to perform a unique role in shaping the educational landscape. Education is the fundamental right of every child. A leader has visionary charismatic personality traits and strategic mindset. Scholar & Ali (2024) stated that, “the positive attitude of a leader has a strong effect on the teachers and students” (p. 5). A leader is a trendsetter, a policy maker and an influencer. The effectiveness of leadership roles in terms of teacher motivation, job satisfaction, and classroom effectiveness. Teacher insights are valuable and portray an educational institute discipline and productive learning environment. Also, the gaps in leadership roles may hinder the progress of a school such as communication, collaboration, and professional development.

Leadership is the ability to motivate people towards a shared vision or goal. School leaders as institutional heads have an important role in enhancing the teachers performance and student’s academic outcomes. An institution head must possess great leadership traits and behaviors to accommodate the teachers as well as learners. This is the primary duty of a school head to motivate teachers and learners. An employee is inspired and follows a leader. So, a leader must possess great leadership characteristics so that the organization flourishes. It is the foremost responsibility of a school head to revolutionize the education system with latest educational reforms such as policies and curriculum within a school system. Adeoye et al. (2025 as cited in Bakker et al., 2023) stated that “transformational leadership in education is a dynamic approach that focuses on accountability, innovation, and global citizenship. It inspires and motivates educators and students to achieve exceptional outcomes” (p. 15).

Zohaib Hassan Sain & Rene. M. Babiera II (2023 as cited in Ahmed et al., 2021) stated that that “A critical point of discussion

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revolves around the country's commitment to international frameworks, notably the Dakar Framework, where developing nations, including Pakistan, pledged to pursue the Education for All (EFA) goal” (p. 3). Furthermore, Zohaib Hassan Sain & Rene. M. Babiera II (2023 as cited in UNESCO, 2022) Pakistan show slow progress towards EFA targets (p. 3). Khadim et al. (2023) reported that Pakistan is one of the emerging nations of the world but faces a big challenge of providing quality education to masses. However, recent times have addressed many significant changes in terms of innovation, technology and also free and fair education systems. New policies, initiatives, and reforms are paving the Pakistani education system to excellence in accordance with global trends (pp. 1-3).

Review of Literature

Adeoye et al. (2025) found that a leader plays a pivotal role in the success of an organization. Adeoye et al. (2025, as cited in Greimel et al., 2023; Saad Alessa, 2021) further emphasized that the impact of transformational leadership style encourages educators to go beyond traditional methods and promote critical thinking, creativity, and student collaboration (p. 15). This perspective highlighted the positive extravagant outcomes of transformational leadership in terms of growth and productivity of the institute. Adeoye et al. (2025, as cited in

Sparks, 2022) laid emphasis on great leadership qualities stating that “transformational leadership, first introduced by James MacGregor Burns in 1978, is a leadership style that encourages followers to prioritise the organisation or community over their self-interests” (p. 15). Mulyani et al. (2020) informed that the effectiveness of any organisation is dependent on the successful attainment of stated goals and objectives and the overall performance (p. 280). It brings to light that an organisation prospers when a leader such as school head and staff members such as teachers work together in a team with devotion and sincerity. Mulyani et al. (2020) elaborated that school effectiveness depends on the standard and quality of education provided. Mulyani et al. (2020) clearly highlighted many studies that pointed out the factors involving school effectiveness are strong and effective principal governance and sustained focus on instruction and learning (p. 280).

Raza et al. (2021) found that there is dominance of private school culture over public schooling in Pakistan. In the absence of a central regulatory authority, private schools independently construct their educational philosophy, influencing curriculum design, pedagogical practices, teacher training, and school operations (pp. 1-2). Raza et al. (2021) further explained that while large school networks often maintain standardized procedures across

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branches, research indicates that criteria for head teacher appointments remain inconsistent and, in many underdeveloped areas, significantly compromised. Extent literature consistently highlighted the pivotal role of school leaders in determining institutional success. Raza et al. (2021 as cited in Böhlmark et al., 2016; Education Review Office, 2018; Felix-Otuorimuo, 2019; Leithwood et al., 2019) found that there exists certain factors associated with head teachers such as effective management, enhanced teacher performance, improved student learning outcomes, and strong community reputation. Raza et al.(2021 as cited in Fullan, 2001) further stated that “effective school leaders are key to large-scale, sustainable education reform” (p. 2). According to Raza et al. (2021) these findings underscore the need to identify the determinants of successful school leadership in Pakistan’s private education sector, where the absence of centralized regulation has resulted in non-standardized practices and fragmented management systems.

According to Sharar & Nawab (2020 as cited in Pont, Nusche, and Moorman, 2008), the success or failure of a school largely depends on the capacity of its leader, which makes school leadership a top priority for educational improvement (p. 2). Jamil et al. (2024 as cited in Hitt & Tucker, 2016) reported that educational leadership,

particularly that provided by head teachers, plays a pivotal role in shaping school culture, ensuring teacher effectiveness, and driving organizational outcomes (p. 85).

Jamil et al. (2024 as cited in Sun & Leithwood, 2015) argued that scholars have increasingly recognized that specific leadership behaviours foster positive teacher attitudes, higher job satisfaction, greater motivation, stronger institutional commitment, and ultimately, improved student achievement (p. 85). Jamil et al. (2024 as cited in Zheng et al., 2019) further informed that however, much of this scholarship has primarily focused on Western contexts, thereby necessitating further exploration within developing countries (p. 85). According to Jamil et al. (2024 as cited in Ashfaq et al., 2018) Pakistan public education sector faces multiple challenges, including low enrollment, high dropout rates, and poor learning outcomes. Government school head teachers, in particular, manage under-resourced institutions, underqualified teaching staff, outdated governance systems, and minimal autonomy. Jamil et al. (2024 as cited in Roncesvalles & Gaerlan, 2021) further highlighted that their leadership, nonetheless, represents a significant level for improving school-level performance.

According to Jamil et al. (2024 as cited in Mansoor, 2015) research on educational leadership in Pakistan and other South Asian contexts, though increasing, remains

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limited compared to Western countries. Existing studies suggest that leadership approaches emphasizing distributed practices, people-centered school cultures, emotional intelligence, and participatory decision-making are positively associated with perceptions of head teacher effectiveness. Jamil et al. (2024 as cited in Kwan, 2020) explained that contemporary scholarship highlights transformational, instructional, and distributed leadership as key frameworks in educational leadership research. Jamil et al. (2024 as cited in Urlick, 2016) pointed out that transformational leadership emphasizes vision building, intellectual stimulation, individualized support, and high expectations. Jamil et al. (2024 as cited in Sun & Leithwood, 2015) explained that instructional leadership focuses on directly enhancing classroom instruction and teacher capacity, while distributed leadership stresses shared responsibilities and collective decision-making. Jamil et al. (2024 as cited in Zheng et al., 2019) further analyzed the integrating elements of these frameworks provides valuable insights into how head teachers influence school outcomes. Cross-cultural evidence further demonstrates that democratic and participatory leadership styles are strongly associated with teacher job satisfaction, including in Turkey and Pakistan.

Jamil et al. (2024 as cited in Harris et al., 2013; Kwan, 2020) found that

transformational and instructional leadership practices have been linked with increased teacher motivation, faculty trust, and self-efficacy in both Western and South Asian contexts. Jamil et al. (2024 as cited in Harris et al., 2013) further informed that head teachers in Pakistan often struggle to reconcile bureaucratic governance structures with more progressive leadership practices. Research suggests that despite systemic limitations, public school leaders in rural areas demonstrate people-focused and relational approaches, leading to incremental improvements in institutional functioning. Zohib Hassan Sain & Rene. M. Babiera II (2023 as cited in Siddiqui and Qureshi 2022) stated that “Private education is accessible, its contribution to national development remains suboptimal” (p. 3).

Karatas et al. (2024) found that the strategies of an effective school lay great emphasis on pedagogical-curricular work, develop teachers’ professional capital, and create a positive learning and teaching environment to increase student’s outcomes. Effective schools engage students and improve students’ academic achievements. Effective schools succeed as they provide an inclusive environment according to learners need. Effective schools sharpen students skills by enforcing a positive learning climate by focusing on long-term goals.

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Intelligence

Pardosi & Utari (2021) found that highly transformational principals have incredible traits to lead and empower the teacher effectively. The transformational leaders value teachers for enhancing school programs.

Influence and Motivation

Pardosi & Utari (2021) clearly pointed out that the principals appreciation has positive impact on the teachers work. Previous research clearly shows that the principals who were approachable and communicated effectively had a great reputation as well and were liked by the teachers. Teamwork correlates positively with commitment to the schools (p. 13).

Vision and Purpose

Abbasi et al. (2025) brought to light the integral role of leadership effectiveness in success of an educational institution in the long run. Teachers view educational heads as the role model that guides, motivates, empowers and supports the teachers professional development and high performance. Abbasi et al. (2025 as cited in Northouse, 2018) informed that the style of leadership mostly influences the teachers effectiveness including various factors involved such as motivation, job satisfaction, and classroom management which is directly related to the students effective outcomes.

Empowerment and Development

Ghori et al. (2025) found that leadership plays a significant role in imparting education in schools such as school climate, teacher effectiveness and student success are all interlinked with the principals. Teachers claim that there must be proper training sessions for teachers to promote education in a most suitable manner (p. 1). Scholar & Ali (2024 as cited in Al-maaitah, 2021) stated that, "The impact of leadership behavior on organizational performance is based on leadership skills like managerial behavior, instructional behavior, vision, courage, communication skills, and decision-making" (p. 6).

Guidance and Direction

Sariakin et al. (2025 as cited in Ainscow, 2023) stated, "As agents of change, teachers not only transfer knowledge but also shape the character and skills needed by students to thrive in society" (p. 2). Denny (2023 as cited in Ciulla & Ciulla, 2020) stated, "Leaders in education are responsible for creating policies and procedures that promote student success, allocating resources effectively, and managing stakeholder relationships (p. 1)."

Integrity and Support

Education is the backbone of a society and a key determinant of economic progress and prosperity in a country. No nation can progress without attaining education. This is the responsibility of academic leader to

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integrate and support the students through stipends, scholarships, free books, laptop schemes etc. Ghorri et al. (2025 as cited in Tuhuteru, Pratiwi, Suryowidiyanti, Mahendika, & Abdullah, 2023) stated, “A nation’s progress is significantly influenced by its education system, which shapes highly qualified human resources. Perceptions of teachers must be understood in order to appreciate the critical role that leadership styles play in creating a successful learning environment at the secondary level. Teachers, as frontline educators, possess valuable perspectives on how leadership influences classroom dynamics, student outcomes, and overall school culture. Teacher performance, a critical indicator of educational achievement, directly impacts the quality of resources produced” (p. 1).

Problem-Solving Skills

Berkat et al. (2025) clearly stated, “An engaging and supportive learning environment is vital for fostering students creativity and critical thinking skills. Educational management must design strategies and tactics that create conducive learning environments, actively involve students, and encourage them to think beyond traditional boundaries. This research is significant in identifying the most effective approaches to nurture a generation that is not only competent but also innovative in addressing global challenges.”

Academic Education of Pakistan

According to (“Problems of Education System in Pakistan: A Critical Analysis and Solution,” 2024) the governmental educational reforms and policies reflect the national ideology of Pakistan. The ideology is the national identity reflected through the core elements of politics, religion, tradition, socio-economic factors and emerging trends in education (pp. 2-3). Hamid (2025) informed that in the realm of 21st century higher educational standards are directly linked to economic growth and prosperity (p. 2). Further Hamid (2025) explained education does not mean bookish knowledge but it must inculcate in an individual the sophisticated competencies and skills to survive (p. 2). According to Faisal Ahmed (2025) Pakistan is the fifth most populous country of the world with almost 255 million population. Mawadat Fatima (2025) reported that the literacy rate is 61 percent that shows steady progress in education with male literacy approximately 68 percent and female literacy rate 52.8 percent. Pakistan educational inconsistencies have shattered economic progress to a large extent. Hamid (2025) further highlighted the issue of high concern the inadequacy and disparities in many areas such as lack of funding, technological problems, rural urban divide, student streaming and government support (pp. 3-4).

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Hamid (2025) found that education enriches people socially, morally, spiritually, politically, and economically. It is an economic indicator of a nation progress and stability. Further Hamid (2025) stated that, *“It is well recognized that countries with well-developed social and political systems and graduates who are playing leadership roles in the community of nations are those that have integrated 21st century skills into their educational systems”* (p.10). Furthermore, (Hamid, 2025) stated that such people are free to exercise their rights, and they are also

Theoretical Framework

politically and economically evolved and free. The key determinant of social rival and instability in Pakistan is the educational system fault as they are unable to sufficiently support the economic progress of the nation. Khadim et al. (2023) *“Education is a means by which a country may advance, cultivating people's sense of accountability and consciousness...Education enables individuals to grasp and actively seek their rights at the national, social, and individual levels”*(p. 1).

Figure 1: *Conceptual Framework for Exploring Teacher Perceptions of Leadership in Public and Private Schools*

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This research paper is based on the following three famous leadership theories that provide framework through which teacher's perceptions can be judged significantly well.

Transformational Leadership Theory

Transformational Leadership Theory was first put forward by Burns (1978). It was further extended by Bass (1985). Kuhnert & Lewis (1987) found that the transformational theory emphasizes the leader role as visionary who inspires, motivates and stimulates their followers towards a common goal.

Application

The research study put forth the effectiveness of transformational leadership style and the difference in the approaches of different sector schools and also the teachers perception in the context of school effectiveness of respective leadership style in this regard.

Research Gap

Through the study of relevant literature, it came to light that the scope of study is limited to particular geographical regions. Certain literature material fails to provide comparative studies. Many research studies focus on teachers performance and student outcomes whereas comparative research solely focusing on teachers perceptions of public and private sector schools remain unexplored. Existing literature fails to address many leadership aspects that need consideration and thorough study.

Literature is full of topics concerning leadership styles and administration outcomes but fails to determine many key areas of teacher interpretation, variations in leadership effectiveness, teacher voices as primary data sources, context specific leadership challenges etc.

Therefore, the literature gaps clearly pointed out towards a teacher-centric investigation of the topic under investigation. The study aims to fill such gaps through comparison of leadership roles and the impact on school culture across both sectors. The study is of high importance as through the addressing of these issues pertaining to educational sector, it will contribute to developing more inclusive leadership models. The ground realities highlighted will help in notifying the concerned educational authorities and governmental agencies to take prompt actions.

The Problem Statement

The role of leadership is crucial in shaping school culture, enhancing teaching strategies and practices, and improving student results or outcomes. However, these aspects have widely been recognized. The area of concern about teacher's perception is limited and needs deliberate research. This kind of qualitative inquiry is crucial as teachers are on the frontline and represent an institute. Their perceptions and personal experiences matter a lot in terms of school context. This study also

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offers a realistic overview of leadership roles and effectiveness of schools.

Research Objective

The aim of the study is to evaluate leadership impact on teaching and learning outcomes.

1. To investigate the school principal roles involving students outcomes related to the teachers behavior, instructional quality, and school climate.

Research Question

RQ: How do teachers perceive the role of school leadership in enhancing school effectiveness, and what leadership practices contribute most to a positive teaching and learning environment?

Significance of Study

By understanding the phenomena of teachers perception on leadership effectiveness school leaders can adapt new strategies to implement and support teaching and learning process in the region. The quality of education will improve enhancing teacher quality. The study can pave the way for policy makers to recognize loopholes in educational systems that need innovation and change. The study is of vital significance as gap between perceived and actual leadership roles can be detected highlighting ground realities to formulate new effective models for future. The Strengths, Weaknesses. Opportunities and Threats (SWOT) analysis can be found out easily through the overview of the study

governing the education setting in different regions of Pakistan.

Limitations of the Study

There lie potential shortcomings in this qualitative inquiry “*Exploring Teacher’s Perception on the Role of Leadership in Public and Private Sector Schools*” highlighted below:

1. The study is limited to particular geographical location i.e., Pakistan.
2. The sample size is small.
3. The certain specific school systems are targeted.
4. The data is based on subjectivity of the teachers perception. There can be potential biases concerning the study.
5. There can be data collection constraint dealing with time limitations, access to certain schools, and willingness of participants can influence the reliability of the results.

Research Methodology

Methodology

This research involves different research techniques, research design and instruments to collect data that will be further analyzed. Research Methodology was utilized to conduct the research on the topic “*Transformational Leadership in Public and Private Schools: A Comparative Study of Teacher Perceptions and Institutional Impact*”. The methodology addresses various phases

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through which the research has been conducted.

Research Design

This Research Design is a qualitative inquiry based on the lived experiences of the participants therefore the research method is of phenomenological nature and purposive sampling technique was utilized. The semi-structured interviews were conducted keeping in view research ethical concerns. Prior to the interview sessions the participants were informed, and consent was taken. Moreover, demographic information was taken for collecting data. Afterwards a detailed semi-structured interview composed of probing questions was conducted to further understand the research subject matter. The phenomenological type of research allows in-depth thorough analysis of the data. This qualitative method is used to understand the subjective nature of study is based on personal experiences and real-life stories of the participants. This method is chosen due to time constraints and also keeping in view the focus of the study. The population includes teachers of both renowned public and private sector schools situated in Pakistan.

Population and Sample

According to Saunders et al. (2020) , “Population refers to the entire set of individuals, events, or objects that share a common characteristic and are of the interest to the researcher” (p. 212). Saunders et al., 2020)

stated that “A sample is the subset of a population selected to represent the whole population” (p. 213). The sample size is 11 and population includes different subject teachers of both Elementary and Higher Secondary Schools belonging to different regions of Pakistan appropriately the provinces of Baluchistan and Sindh. Among 11 participants of education sector there are five females of government sector, 2 females of private sector schools, 1 male of government sector, 3 males of private sector schools.

Target Population: Data is collected from 11 different schools both public and private situated in Pakistan in which different areas of Baluchistan and Sindh were targeted. The targeted sample belonged to the teaching staff. The selection criteria were based on the expertise, experience and qualifications of teachers in the field of academic education in the schools.

Research Tools and Techniques: The purposive sampling technique was utilized, and various research tools were used for the collection of data including electronic devices, digital gadgets, manual tools and softwares.

Digital Tools

Electronic Gadgets: Various digital gadgets were used with high power internet access and recording options such as laptops, mobile phones and tablets.

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Audio Devices: For the purpose of recording the interview audio devices were used such as mics, phone and laptop audio recorders etc.

Cloud-based data storage: For data security reasons cloud-based researcher personal google drive was used.

Documentation Tools: For data recording, transcript and documentation purpose various Microsoft Office such as MS Word and WPS softwares were used. For transcription turboscribe.ai online tool was used.

Social Media Apps: For the communication and collaboration of group members including the participants various social media forums were used such as WhatsApp Groups, instant messaging and calling includes Mobilink and ZonG mobile services.

Instant Massaging: The group members constantly collaborated and shared information with one another, attaching files and sending through personal email ids or Whats App.

Thematic Analysis: For meaningful interpretation of data research underwent different stages initial codes were developed based-on the data collected i.e., the interview transcripts and afterwards meaningful codes such as themes were generated in order to further generate key findings. The thematic analysis helped in understanding the topic and scope of research study.

Triangulation: The triangulation aspect was used, and many different sources were utilized that enhanced the credibility of the research.

Ethical Considerations: The research was conducted keeping in view research ethical guidelines such as informed consent, data security and confidentiality and data surveillance etc.

Data Analysis and Findings

Analysis of Data

Data Analysis involved few steps. First of all, an interview questionnaire composed of various questions was designed. Informed consent was taken putting in view research ethics. Prior to the interview sessions demographic data was collected for authenticity of research, Secondly, Semi-structured interviews were taken live using Zoom meetings, phone calls, Whats App Business and online recording was saved on Google Drive. Next, thematic analysis was carried out. In this regard, a codebook was created composed of a table column including initial codes, refined codes, description/memos, that helped in the generation of meaningful interpretation of themes.

Discussion and Findings

Total number of eleven semi-structured interviews were conducted by the respective group members the population sample included various teachers of both public and private sector renowned schools. The research questions were used to

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conceptualize a codebook. Based on the research questions following key themes were generated. The interview with participant teachers provided valuable insights into teachers' perceptions of leadership practices in both private and public sector schools in Pakistan. Several key themes emerged, which are presented below:

Theme 1: Effective Leadership

There were different perceptions regarding the role of a leader as portrayed through a teacher's vision. Respondent 1 pointed out that, "*Good leadership play an effective role in development teaching, learning process, students benefits and education institute also.*" On the other hand, respondent 2 perception about leadership role is depicted as, "*School leadership supports professional growth.*"

Theme 2: Professional Growth

Most of the teachers appreciated the efforts of their school principals. The various teacher training sessions include training sessions, workshops, IPD training sessions, LSBE sessions etc. for professional growth of teachers. As respondent 10 conveyed a positive message, "*Yeah, definitely! Leadership offer training, development programs, encourage your teamwork, collaboration etc.*"

Another of the respondent 3 brought to light through such remarks, "*...it does help in my personal goals because I want to teach the students, I want to spread knowledge so with the school and the teaching profession I can do that better.*"

Theme 3: Student Academic Outcomes

A teacher plays a pivotal role in student's academic standings and extraordinary performance results. The students success in educational fields is mostly dependent on a teacher's keen attention and content delivery of interactive lessons for learners. In this regard respondent 4 laid emphasis on active role of teacher such as providing right guidance, support, and good subject knowledge.

Theme 4: Leadership Style

A school head must possess certain qualities such as intelligence, trust, empathy, problem-solving skills, excellent interpersonal skills, discipline, time management etc.

Theme 5: Empathy

The educators follow principals instruction. So, good leadership leads to mutual trust and good relationships among leaders and subordinates, fostering productivity and growth of the workplace. Respondent 6 urged the need for mutual respect, understanding and encouragement can benefit both. The respondent 5 remarked, "*We are following, and we are seeing the role model.*"

Theme 6: Innovation and Creativity

Innovation and creativity are the basic essence of education. Education makes a learner expressive, confident and self-aware. Education is not about reading books and learning but most importantly making

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young minds develop ethics and responsible citizens.

Theme 7: Marketing and Reputation

Through the interview sessions public vs private sector schoolteachers, it came to light that private schools are more focused on marketing and reputation such as social media etc. On the other hand, government schools are less concerned about these issues mainly due to limited budgets and pre-determined educational policies. In this regard respondent 6 replied, *“Yes! If I talk about my perspective...private sectors have to be careful about their reputation. They are marketing regularly...and are hiring different marketing managers to promote their business...but they are also focusing on education.”* Another respondent 9 stated, *“In the public sector they focus on quality education.”*

Theme 8: Accountability

A good leader is supportive and sincere in their profession. The interview coding brought to light that public sector school leaders have to follow preset rules and regulations. On the other hand, there is less government intervention in private sector schools.

Theme 9: School Culture

As stated by famous thinker Allan Bloom, *“Education is the movement from darkness to light.”* So, education transforms a person, it breeds confidence and intelligence. So, a school is a place of learning where a student must exhibit an uplift character.

School is just like a place of worship where high aimed learners are motivated to learn and grow.

Theme 10: Productivity

An effective organization sets clear long-term goals and implements strategies. Denny (2023) laid great emphasis on revolutionizing the educational system under the supervision of an ideal leader impacting the education stakeholders such as teachers outcomes, student’s academic performance and overall quality of education. As pointed out by the respondent 7, *“He provides all the resources and maintains the discipline... The students receive good instruction and guidance in this way. As long as the teachers are motivated and confident, both will benefit from it.”*

Theme 11: Workplace Conflict Management

A leader must know how to deal with different situations as well as staff. A school head must show unbiased in attitude resulting in a positive workplace environment. According to respondent 8, *“She should communicate well...she should arrange meetings, make policies and guidelines for everyone.”*

Theme 12: Preference of Choice

It was a tough decision for respondents, some preferred private schools whereas others were determined to work for the talented deserving young minds. According to the respondent 10, *“The ideal school, if we talk according to the work, all the things that*

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should be in a good school, are seen in private schools.” Another respondent 1 stated, “I prefer the public school, because private school students have more opportunities to learn more things. which are very expensive. But the public sector students no opportunities...their parents have low income, and they don’t gather more knowledge from the expensive institutes. They have only one and only choice, their school...so, I prefer public school to train those who need more.”

Conclusion and Recommendation

Conclusion

This study has underscored the perceived roles of school leaders as depicted through the educator lens. The school head lays the foundation for generations ahead to inculcate a sense of wisdom, knowledge and responsibility. But alas many government schools are facing disruptions in terms of technological gaps, poor infrastructure, governmental policies and insufficient reform system support. The key findings reveal potential gaps in terms of public and private sector schools. The bridging gap could only be negotiated through effective dialogue of school leaders, administration and management and also through intervention of government. The research clearly highlighted the attention of higher authority to empower and encourage teacher participation in decision making. The founder of nation Quaid E Azam Mohammad Ali Jinnah in one of his powerful messages about education said,

“The world is moving so fast that if you do not educate yourselves, you will not only be completely left behind but will be finished up.” The world is moving towards advancement, and education is the glory of a nation. Nelson Mandela one of the influential leaders of 20th century once said, “Education is the most powerful weapon which you can use to change the world.” This is an important piece of research about an emerging education issue.

Recommendation

The findings reveal many realities faced by the educational system today in the realm of 21st century. Recommendations can be prioritized to enhance effectiveness of leadership within a school context in accordance with global challenges pertaining to the educational systems both public and private sector schools. Leadership practices can be aligned properly with teachers expectations. This paper highlights issues that need deliberate solutions in order to empower educational systems. The educational systems must be upgraded with latest methods and techniques of both teaching and learning. Hamid (2025) informed that the Pakistani educational systems must revolutionize through scientific and technical development of infrastructures. Pakistan is although a developing country needs to develop significantly to meet the demand of globalized world undergoing digital transformation (p. 5). Hamid (2025) clearly

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stated that “the teachers training programs must be flexible and moreover up to date to meet the demand of the modern era” (p. 6). Rind & Malin (2024) informed that the education must be made inclusive for all learners. Increasing enrollment rate and focus on quality not quantity of lectures. Empower educators through continuous professional development training. There must be incentives for the students. According to the ARY NEWS (2025) the School Education and Literacy Department initiative of free textbooks, stipends, STEM and STEAM-based learning etc. to educate the needy students is a move towards a brighter and prosperous future ahead.

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